

How to Protect Your Family's Wealth

If you're like most people, you've probably accumulated a few important assets over your lifetime, whether that's a home, a car, or a savings account. We've put together a list of 3 ways you can protect those assets from creditors, lawsuits, and bankruptcy.

1. Open an irrevocable trust

Utilizing irrevocable trusts has long been known as an effective asset protection strategy. It works because transferring assets to an irrevocable trust moves them out of the grantor's estate, meaning they're no longer legally considered to be in the grantor's ownership. As such, they're more protected. You can learn more about irrevocable trusts at

<https://domesticassettrust.com/revocable-vs-irrevocable-trusts/>

2. Own an indivisible interest in your home

Another asset protection strategy worth considering is titling your home (and other assets) in such a way as to offer them more protection from lawsuits and bankruptcy. Depending on your state, if you own an indivisible interest in your home, it may be protected. Check with a lawyer to be sure, as it depends on various factors.

3. Transfer money to your IRA

How much of your wealth do you plan on using before you turn 59.5 years old? If the answer is 'not all of it', you might want to move the excess over to your IRA or another retirement plan. These plans are often protected entities so the money you put in is protected from debt collectors and bankruptcy. Check the specifics with a lawyer/financial expert to confirm this for your personal circumstances.